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Gender Gap in the Critical Infrastructure Research Community

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Abstract. A significant gender gap persists in STEM fields across many developed countries, despite encouraging policies. To develop effective solutions that narrow the gender gap in these fields, a deeper understanding of the root causes is essential. Quantifying the disparity is a crucial first step in any analysis. Specifically, we focus on the critical infrastructure sector. Our research delves into the participation of women in this domain by examining articles and conference proceedings published between 2006 and 2022 in the CRITIS conference. We meticulously analyzed the presence of women and their roles in these events to gain insights into gender representation, dynamics, and contribution within this field. To perform an automated gender identification based on names, we used a software called Cerbero-Lite. This takes names from dblp (developed at University of Trier in 1993) as input, extracts the first names, and, then, uses the Harvard Dataset to predict their genders. Subsequently, we performed a gendered assessment of the community by means of advanced social network analysis techniques. The research shows that, while a significant gender gap in favor of males exists in terms of participation, it does not reflect a difference in the ability of females to contribute to the development of the field.

Keywords: Critical Infrastructure, Gender, Social Network Analysis

1 Introduction

Throughout history, women have always been discriminated against compared to men. Unfortunately, even today in the 21st century, even in so-called developed societies, we witness all sorts of discrimination and prejudiced attitudes towards women, despite the fact that they are an integral and indispensable part of society. Even by looking at simple statistical data, it is easy to see that female employment rates are lower than male ones. Certain fields, particularly in the scientific realm, which were historically dominated by men, such as engineering, medicine, and science in general, now categorized under STEM (acronym of Science Technology Engineering Mathematics), were once off-limits to women. Those few women who managed to enroll in universities had to fight against

immense challenges and deep-rooted prejudices. This was partly due to the prevailing notion, still held by some today, that men and women possess different abilities and aptitudes, making some fields more suitable for one gender than the other. Indeed, a glance at labor data reveals a stark disparity: women are heavily represented in the fields of care and education, while men dominate domains like politics, science, computer science, and mathematics.

In this paper, we analyze the role of women in the critical infrastructure (CI) field, which heavily relies on STEM subjects. Our primary objective is to determine whether a gender gap exists in this field by analyzing data and identifying disparities in representation, opportunities, and roles. Additionally, we aim to evaluate the evolution of the gender gap in the sector over the years. We used data from the International Conference on Critical Information Infrastructures Security (CRITIS), a leading event for CI practitioners and researchers, covering the period from 2006 to 2022. Our analysis identifies trends and assesses whether the gender gap has been widening, narrowing, or remaining stagnant.

We can identify the following five research questions. (RQ1) As a group, are females and males equally contributing to the development of the CI field? (RQ2) As a group, are females and males equally essential to the larger CI community, (RQ3) As a group, have females and males different sources of inspiration? (RQ4) As a group, are females and males equally successful? (RQ5) As a group, are females and males equally creative?

Let us not forget that an equitable society is one of the core objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). A society that provides equal opportunities for all fosters an environment brimming with diverse perspectives and inputs, which in turn facilitates breakthroughs and problem-solving. The aim of this paper is to examine the prevalence of the gender equity issue and bring it to light, thereby prompting governments to implement effective policies for its resolution. To this purpose, in our research, we used Cerbero-lite, a name-based gender disambiguation software created for the gEneSys European project [?], along with the gender divide assessment framework described in [?].

This rest of the paper is organized as it follows. Section 2 presents the related work. Section 3 discusses the methodology and software for gender gap assessment. The data analyzed and the results are described in Section 4. The discussion is provided in Section 5 and, finally, Section 6 concludes the paper with some recommendations for the future.

2 Related Works

Several studies have examined the participation of women in communities. For example, Di Tommaso et al. [?] used social network analysis to study gender disparities in enterprises. Similarly, De Nicola & De Agostino [?] [?] defined and applied a gender divide assessment framework based on social network analysis to evaluate four scientific communities within computer science and information systems. The proposed framework considers three dimensions: context, discipline, and community. Context refers to the operating environment of commu-

nity members. Discipline defines the specific domain being analyzed. Community encompasses characteristics derived from social relationships, collaborations, and the ratio of females to males. A study by Kane et al. [?] examines gender bias on Wikipedia by analyzing data on profiles of female and male Fortune 1000 CEOs. The researchers specifically looked at how editors on Wikipedia, a collaborative online encyclopedia, interacted with these pages. Their findings were unexpected: gender bias on Wikipedia seemed to favor feminine CEOs over their male counterparts. This research (by Kane et al.) presents a method of analysis using real-world data collected from publicly available web information and editor behavior on Wikipedia. Continuing our exploration of gender and online collaboration, a study by Mennecke et al. [?] examines how gender differences manifest in virtual environments during creative tasks. This research explores how gender might influence teamwork and creative outcomes within virtual spaces.

Abramo et al [?] investigated the impact of Covid-19 on scientific production. These studies primarily focused on changes in preprint submissions (arXiv, bioRxiv, medRxiv) before and after the pandemic. Notably, Abramo et al. found a similar decrease in research output for both females and males, particularly in Europe and North America. Social network analysis, as evidenced by research in this field, offers a valuable tool to study both these aspects – people’s behavior in online collaboration and the evolution of creative fields within social network platforms. D’Agostino & De Nicola [?] studied researcher’s resilience during the Covid-19 pandemic. The resilience is defined as the capacity or ability of a researcher to adapt, recover, and bounce back from challenges, setbacks, or adversity. This allows them to continue pursuing their scientific activities. Specifically, the study aimed to investigate whether there was a gender gap in resilience, and no significant differences were observed. A recent report by the EU Commission [?] explored the broader impact of Covid-19 on academic activities. Their findings highlighted a concerning gender disparity: women submitted manuscripts at a lower rate than expected compared to their pre-pandemic submissions in the same period of 2018 and 2019. Additionally, the number of female first authors decreased by 19% compared to publications in the same journals during 2019. This resulted in a widening gender gap of 14 percentage points for first authorship.

With respect to the cited papers, the study in this article aims to investigate the gender gap in the field of critical infrastructure, an area that has not yet been addressed by other studies.

3 Methodology and Software for Gender Gap Assessment

3.1 Gender assessment framework

In a study of De Nicola & D’Agostino [?], the authors defined the gender divide assessment framework, which is structured in three dimension: the context, the attitude and the success. The first dimension, the context regards the environment in which community members engage. Examples of the corresponding indicators are gender ratio, degree, and network centrality indices. The gender ratio

and degree measure, respectively, the percentage of females and males and the number of coauthors. Other examples of network centrality indices are betweenness, closeness, and eigenvector centrality (see Table 1). The second dimension is the attitude and examples of the indicators are susceptibility of authors to the topics treated in the papers of their co-authors or in the conference papers as a whole, novelty, and combinational creativity. Novelty measures the researcher's capacity to generate innovative and fitting work. Combinational creativity quantifies a researcher's aptitude for merging distinct topics. For the third dimension, the success, which pertains to the attainment of objectives, examples of the indicators are number of papers, charges, and the authority. The number of papers measures the average number of papers authored or co-authored by researcher. The authority quantifies the degree to which the topics discussed in an author's paper exert influence on the topics explored in the papers of their coauthors.

A summary of a selection of the indices used in this analysis is presented in Table 1.

Index	Description
Authority	Authority measures to what extent the topics in an author's papers influence the topics in his/her coauthors' papers.
Betweenness	Betweenness (B) [?] measures how important were a node if all of them would try to communicate along the network by the shortest path. That is, supposing anyone sends a message to anyone, how many of such messages pass through a node.
Charges	Number of positions of responsibility for controlling or caring for something. Examples could be the role of a scientist inside an organization (e.g., Full Professor) or a community.
Closeness	Closeness measures the average harmonic distance for a member to reach any other member of the community [?].
Combinational creativity	Combinational creativity measures the ability of a researcher to combine different topics [?]. It is given by the number of times he/she has been the one that combined two topics for the first time.
Degree	Number of coauthors of a member of the community.
EigenCentrality	EigenCentrality [?] can be interpreted as the probability of news to reach a node upon spreading on the network.
Gender ratio	Gender ratio allows to measure the female to male ratio.
Neighbour susceptibility	This index measures to what extent the topics in an author's papers are influenced by the topics in his/her coauthors' papers.
Novelty	Novelty measures the ability of a researcher to produce work that is both novel (i.e., original, unexpected) and appropriate (i.e., useful, adaptive concerning task constraints) [?]. It is given by the number of times he/she has been the one that introduced a topic for the first time.
Number of papers	Number of papers written by a researcher.
Trend susceptibility	Trend susceptibility measures to what extent the topics in an author's papers are influenced by the topics in the conference papers as a whole.

Table 1. Summary of a selection of the indices presented in [?].

3.2 A Software for Name-based Gender Disambiguation

In this work, we analyzed a set of articles extracted from dblp³ by using a gender automated disambiguation software called Cerbero-Lite. The software takes as input a list of names, determines which is the first name and through Harvard Dataset [?] assigns a gender probability. Figure 1 represents the architecture of Cerbero Lite. From a software standpoint, the Cerbero-Lite process operates as illustrated in Figure 1 and elaborated below. Bibliometric data for a sample of papers are retrieved from a scientific online database, i.e., DBLP. The data are then cleaned and imported (1) into the disambiguation manager. Subsequently, the disambiguation manager extracts the name from the full name. The previously acquired HARVARD World Gender Name Dictionary (WGND 2.0) [?] is employed to correlate the name with a gender probability. The WGND 2.0 is a compilation of names from various countries, categorized by gender. For each author, the software can assign three gender likelihoods: the likelihood that the author is male, female, or of undetermined gender. This system has been used to analyze female participation in the CRITIS conference and to assess overall conference participation.

Fig. 1. Architecture of Cerbero Lite

4 Analysis of data

4.1 Gender dynamics in the CRITIS community

To capture the evolving dynamics of gender representation, our study spans a substantial timeframe, encompassing articles published between 2006 and 2022. This extensive time range enables us to identify trends and patterns in females' participation and roles within the critical infrastructure sector over nearly two decades.

³ dblp computer science bibliography url: <https://dblp.org>

As mentioned in Section 3, the procedure followed was as follows. First, data were extracted using dblp that provides open access to bibliographic information for major computer science publications (journals and conference and workshop proceedings). Then, they were filtered using a software program. Once the files with the names were obtained, Cerbero-Lite was used to disambiguate the gender. After, we computed the percentages of participation by men, women, and undetermined individuals, year by year from 2006 to 2022.

Table 2 shows the number and the corresponding rates of males, females, and undetermined by year. There is a significant gender gap and a consistent trend over time. Similarly, Figure 2 depicts the gender rates by year. Upon examining it, a significant gender gap becomes evident. The rate for males remains around 80% and stays consistent throughout the examined period, except for a slight dip between 2008 and 2010. Regarding females, the rate remains around 20%. For authors with undetermined gender, the rate is insignificant, demonstrating Cerbero-lite’s capability in name-based gender disambiguation.

Years	n_m	n_f	n_u	%Males	%Females	%Undet.
2006	57	6	2	87.69%	9.23%	3.08%
2007	118	18	4	84.29%	12.86%	2.86%
2008	198	45	6	79.52%	18.07%	2.41%
2009	244	52	7	80.53%	17.16%	2.31%
2010	272	55	7	81.44%	16.47%	2.10%
2011	298	66	7	80.32%	17.79%	1.89%
2012	335	72	10	80.34%	17.27%	2.40%
2013	374	80	11	80.43%	17.20%	2.37%
2014	458	99	15	80.07%	17.31%	2.62%
2015	508	107	17	80.38%	16.93%	2.69%
2016	552	125	21	79.08%	17.91%	3.01%
2017	602	134	24	79.21%	17.63%	3.16%
2018	642	141	25	79.46%	17.45%	3.09%
2019	692	154	25	79.45%	17.68%	2.87%
2020	698	156	27	79.23%	17.71%	3.06%
2021	723	162	29	79.10%	17.72%	3.17%
2022	782	169	31	79.63%	17.21%	3.16%

Table 2. Number and rates of males (n_m , %Males), females (n_f , %Females), undetermined (n_u , %Undet.) scientists participating at the CRITIS conference by year.

4.2 Centrality of CRITIS scientists in the community

By exploiting the coauthorship relationship emerging from the papers written together by authors, a community of scientists can be represented as a social network [?] [?]. For the CRITIS community, the emerging social network is depicted in Figure 3. Blue circles represent males while purple circles females. The size of each circle is proportional to the node degree. The figure clearly shows a large group of 202 researchers working together in this field, along with several smaller ones. There are three other prominent groups consisting of more than 20 scientists: 23, 28, and 34 individuals, respectively. It is worthy to observe that the rates of males and females are, respectively, 74,75% and 25,25%. Hence,

Fig. 2. Gender rates of scientists participating at the CRITIS conference by year.

the situation in the largest group is better for females with respect to that in the wider CRITIS community.

A network representation allows for the application of advanced techniques typically used in complex network analysis. Specifically, we measured four indicators to capture different aspects of network centrality: average betweenness (\bar{B}), average closeness (\bar{C}), average degree (\bar{D}), and average eigenvector centrality (\bar{E}). Table 3 presents the corresponding values. Although \bar{B} for females is higher than for males, these differences are not statistically significant, as shown in Figure 5. The average degree, \bar{D} , favors females when considering either all authors or only the semantically treatable ones (see, respectively, \bar{D}_A and \bar{D}_T in Table 3). Semantically treatable (T) authors are defined as those who have written at least two papers in two different years [?]. However, the differences between the average values for males and females are only weakly statistically significant. In contrast, both closeness (\bar{C}) and eigenvector centrality (\bar{E}) favor females and these differences are highly statistically significant.

4.3 Susceptible scientists

By following the approach presented in [?], we analyzed the diffusion of interests in various topics and estimated neighbour susceptibility (x_i) and trend susceptibility (x_{si}) for each semantically treatable member of the CRITIS community.

Fig. 3. CRITIS social network emerging from coauthorship relationships

Gender	B	Cl	\bar{D}_A	\bar{D}_T	\bar{E}
Females	0.000147	0.0197	5.04	8.00	0.0108
Males	0.000134	0.0142	4.55	7.04	0.0045

Table 3. Comparison of the average values of the main centrality indices.

Table 4 presents the obtained values. For x_i , the average value for females is 0.042, while for males, it is 0.059. This suggests that females are generally less influenced by their coauthors compared to males, although the difference is only weakly statistically significant. Conversely, the average trend susceptibility value is higher for females, with this difference also being weakly statistically significant.

Gender	\bar{x}	\bar{x}_s	\bar{a}
Females	0.042	0.114	0.132
Males	0.059	0.088	0.108

Table 4. Comparison of the average values of the susceptibility indices and authority for semantically treatable values. Average susceptibility to neighbours: \bar{x} ; average susceptibility to trends: \bar{x}_s ; average authority: (\bar{a}).

4.4 Success of CRITIS scientists

Success of authors can be assessed by checking their scientific production, and the recognition by the community. Here, we have identified some indicators that can be used for the purpose. Table 5 includes the average number of papers of males (\bar{p}_m), of females (\bar{p}_f), and of undetermined (\bar{n}_u) authors as well as the average number of papers of semantically treatable masculine ($\bar{p}_{T,m}$) and of feminine authors ($\bar{p}_{T,f}$). \bar{p}_m is 1.415 while \bar{p}_f is 1.408. These values are similar and there is not a statistically significant difference. Similarly, for semantically treatable authors, we can note a value of 3.059 for males and 2.889 for females. Even if this suggests that males tend to write more articles over the years also this difference is not statistically significant.

\bar{p}_m	\bar{p}_f	\bar{p}_u	$\bar{p}_{T,m}$	$\bar{p}_{T,f}$
1.415	1.408	1.354	3.059	2.889

Table 5. Average number of papers of males (\bar{p}_m), average number of papers of females (\bar{p}_f), and average number of papers of undetermined (\bar{n}_u), average number of papers of T (semantically treatable) males ($\bar{p}_{T,m}$), and average number of papers of T females ($\bar{p}_{T,f}$).

After analyzing the average of written papers for each author categorized by gender, we investigated if there is gender gap in the organizational roles of CRITIS conference. The information was extracted from the Springer proceedings books, after cleaning the data. Particularly, we considered the program committees, the chairs roles, and some other secondary roles, such as participation to the local organization committee.

	n_m	n_f	n_u	%Males	%Females	%Undet
Chairs	65	15	0	85.52%	14.47%	0.00%
Members	216	42	13	79.70%	15.49%	4.79%
Secondary	56	34	4	59.57%	36.17%	4.25%

Table 6. Number of males (n_m), females (n_f), and undetermined (n_u) and corresponding rates (%Males, %Females, and %Undet), respectively, for chairs, members, and secondary roles.

Table 6 clearly demonstrates that the number of females is consistently far lower than that of males. Moreover, the gap widens when considering leadership positions such as chairs, where females represent only 14%. This presents a significant challenge, as achieving equity is one of the fundamental goals towards a more progressive and sustainable society.

Figure 4 presents the number of memberships on the x-axis and the number of chairs on the y-axis. The graph uses circles that increase in size as the number of people filling those roles increases. Blue circles represent males, purple circles represent females, and gray circles represent an equal number of males and females in those roles. We observe that in most cases, the largest circle is always the one representing males, with the purple circle represented within it. Furthermore, if we look at the people who have most frequently held the roles of chairs and members, we always see blue spheres indicating males. This indicates a clear presence of a gender gap in all these conference roles.

Finally, the average authority of semantically treatable authors is in favor of females (see Table 4). However, the difference between the average value for females and for males is weakly statistically significant.

4.5 Creativity of CRITIS scientists

Creativity in conceiving new ideas and technology is one of the elements required to disrupt science and technology. To assess creativity of CRITIS members, we measured four indicators: the number of scientists that were the first to introduce a topic, the number of scientists that were the first to combine two topics, the novelty index (\bar{N}), and the combinational creativity index (\bar{C}) [?]. We recall that $\mathcal{N}_{h_i} = \frac{1}{N_{c_k}} \cdot \sum_{c_k} \frac{\delta_{k,i}}{n_{c_k}}$ where $\delta_{k,i} = 1$ if the author h_i was one of the first authors to propose the topic c_k ; $\delta_{k,i} = 0$ if the author h_i was not one of the first authors to propose the topic c_k ; n_{c_k} is the number of the authors that first proposed the topic c_k ; and N_{c_k} is the overall number of topics. This index spans the [0,1]

Fig. 4. Relationships between number of member roles and number of chair roles. The size of the balls is proportional to number of masculine (blue) and feminine (purple) scientists.

range. Then, $C_{h_i} = \frac{1}{N_{p_{kl}}} \cdot \sum_{p_{kl}} \frac{\delta_{p_{kl},i}}{n_{p_{kl}}}$, where p_{kl} is the pair of topics (c_k, c_l) ; $\delta_{p_{kl},i} = 1$ if the author h_i was one of the first authors to propose p_{kl} ; $\delta_{p_{kl},i} = 0$ if the author h_i was not one of the first authors to propose p_{kl} ; $n_{p_{kl}}$ is the number of the authors that first proposed p_{kl} ; and $N_{p_{kl}}$ is the overall number of detected pairs of topics. Also this index spans the $[0,1]$ range. While the first pairs of indicators measure how many authors are creative, $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ and $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$ measure the extent of their creativity.

Table 7 presents the values for the above-mentioned indicators. Considering only the disambiguated authors, males are 82,23% and females 17,7%. The percentage of masculine scientists that were the first to introduce a topic is 79.29% whereas the percentage of feminine ones is 20.71%. The percentage of feminine scientists that were the first to combine two topics is 18.36% whereas the percentage of masculine ones is 81.64%. Finally, both $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ and $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$ are in favor of males. However, the differences of $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ are not statistically significant while the differences of $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$ are weakly statistically significant.

4.6 Note on the statistical significance of results

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the distribution of the average number of papers in random samples for both females and males. This helps estimate the likelihood

Gender	Ratio	\mathcal{N} authors	\mathcal{C} authors	$\bar{\mathcal{N}}$	$\bar{\mathcal{C}}$
Females	17.77%	20.71%	18.36%	0.00101	0.0009
Males	82.23%	79.29%	81.64%	0.00103	0.0010

Table 7. Results of the creativity analysis and average number of papers for the CRITIS community. \mathcal{N} authors are the authors introducing novel topics. \mathcal{C} authors are the authors introducing novel combinations of topics. $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ is the average novelty index. $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$ is the average combinational creativity index. \bar{p} is the average number of papers.

that the observed deviations for the female group are not due to chance. To create these figures, we randomly sampled authors 100,000 times. The figures use vertical lines to represent the average indicator values for different groups: pink (F) for females (ind_F), blue (M) for males (ind_M), and gray (U) for authors with undetermined gender (ind_U). The black line (R) represents the average value for random samples (ind_R). To generate the control group results, we first calculated the average value for each of the 100,000 random samples. The control group’s mean is then the average of all these individual sample averages, with the standard deviation (σ) reflecting the spread of values within this distribution of sample averages. The hypothesis was considered highly significant if the deviation of the female average value was greater than $5/2 \cdot \sigma$, significant if the deviation was between $3/2 \cdot \sigma$ and $5/2 \cdot \sigma$, and weakly significant if the deviation was between $\sigma/2$ and $3/2 \cdot \sigma$. It was rejected if the deviation was less than $\sigma/2$.

It is important to note that if the hypothesis of a gender gap for an indicator is not statistically significant, this does not mean the findings are invalid. Instead, it indicates that there is no gender gap for that particular indicator.

5 Discussion

(RQ1) As a group, are females and males equally contributing to the development of the critical infrastructure field?

Based on the analyzed data, we can observe the presence of significant gender gap. Males are contributing much more than females, since most of the authors are males. Particularly, analyzing the set of articles published between 2006 and 2022, the rate of males remains about 80% while the rate for females is about 20%. Over the years, the gap has remained constant or has experienced only a slight temporary decline.

(RQ2) As a group, are females and males equally essential to the larger community?

While degree simply tells us how many connections a member of a community has, other measures like betweenness, eigencentrality, and closeness go beyond that. These latter metrics focus on the likelihood of new information, like a topic, reaching a particular member. They achieve this by considering the network’s structure and how a member is positioned within it. In essence, these measures

Fig. 5. Distribution of sample averages of the betweenness, closeness, degree of random samples for all the authors and for semantically treatable (T) ones, eigenvector centrality, and authority.

Fig. 6. Distribution of sample averages of the number of papers for all the authors and for semantically treatable (T) ones, novelty, combinational creativity, neighbour susceptibility, and trend susceptibility.

tell us how important a member’s position is for the spread of information within the community. To answer this question we can observe Table 3. Indeed, we have to consider four indicators, respectively: betweenness (\bar{B}), closeness (\bar{C}), degree (\bar{D}), and eigenvector centrality (\bar{E}). \bar{C} , \bar{D} , \bar{D}_T , and \bar{E} are in favor of females. This means that, despite they are fewer, females are more central than males.

(RQ3) As a group, have females and males different sources of inspiration? Observing Table 4, we note that while the values of neighbour susceptibility (x_i) are lower for females, those of trend susceptibility (x_{si}) are higher. This indicates that females tend to be more influenced by trends than by their coauthors compared to males.

(RQ4) As a group, are females and males equally successful?

The issue of success within the CRITIS community is somewhat controversial. The differences in productivity, measured by the average number of papers published, are not statistically significant when considering either the entire CRITIS community or the most regular conference participants. However, leadership roles tend to favor males. Key positions such as chair and member roles are predominantly held by males, and although the situation is somewhat better for females in secondary organizational roles, a significant gender gap still exists. Interestingly, among the most regular participants, females are perceived as more authoritative. This suggests that despite their lower numbers, the females who do regularly participate are highly respected and considered leaders within the community.

(RQ5) As a group, are females and males equally creative?

Considering the proportions of males and females, as well as the number of scientists who were the first to introduce a new topic or combine two topics, the data reveal that the number of creative females is higher than expected. In terms of the extent of creativity, we did not find significant differences between males and females for novelty. However, we found weakly statistically significant differences favoring males in their ability to combine topics.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a study on the participation of females and males in the critical infrastructure field. We posed five research questions to analyze the potential gender gap, focusing on three dimensions of scientific activities: context, success, and attitude. Our dataset was extracted from the CRITIS conference proceedings, covering the period from the conference’s inception in 2006 to 2022. We specifically considered the papers, their authors, the committees, and the various chairs. We employed Cerbero-lite, a software for name-based gender disambiguation developed as part of the European project gEneSys, and the gender divide assessment framework presented in [?]. Despite an ongoing im-

balance in participation favoring males, our research indicates that females have equal potential to contribute to the development of this field. To increase the presence of females in the critical infrastructure field, we suggest implementing policies such as special awards for females and mandatory quotas in committees and chair roles. These measures would ensure more proportionate female representation at conferences, thereby raising their visibility and profile in the field and bringing new perspectives for the advancement of security of critical information infrastructures.

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